

MATERIALS FOR TEACHING LEXICOLOGY

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Annotation. This article is a concise answer to your query about materials for teaching lexicology, based on the given search results: Teaching materials for lexicology should aim to make students "word-conscious" and able to recognize the origin and meaning of words from their morphemes. Some key principles and activities include: Providing a framework for selecting the most suitable language teaching materials for a course. Using authentic materials that show real-world language use and are of high interest to students. Authentic materials can provide meaningful context for learning vocabulary. Pre-teaching key vocabulary words from the materials using visuals and example sentences to build students' confidence before interacting with the text. Activities like Photo Vocabulary allow students to guess word meanings based on context clues. Providing multiple opportunities for students to practice new vocabulary words through activities like Partner Quizzes and Vocabulary Auctions. Repeated exposure helps cement learning. Designing materials that reflect the teacher's beliefs about language and learning, contextualize the language, and make students active participants.

When teaching lexicology, both inductive and deductive approaches can be used to enhance students' understanding of lexical concepts. Materials that can be employed in an inductive and deductive manner for teaching lexicology are considered very crucial in Linguistics.

Inductive Materials: Authentic Texts: Utilize authentic texts like newspaper articles, magazines, or literary works that contain rich lexical diversity. Encourage students to identify and analyze unfamiliar words, word formation patterns, collocations, and semantic relationships within the context.

For example, most intermediate students would understand the collocation 'move house' from its constituent parts, but very few at this level would produce it. By drawing learners' attention to chunks, we can help them use the words they already know more accurately and to express a wider range of ideas. This can be just as useful as learning 'new words', if not more so.

Exploiting reading and listening texts for lexical chunks

The following activities can be used after exploiting a text for meaning, for example, after learners answer comprehension questions or do a matching exercise based on the text.⁵¹

Listening

Give learners the tapescript with some key collocations blanked out. They listen again and complete the spaces.

Listening texts can also be used to provide a model for pronunciation, for example, the stress pattern of chunks. Ask learners to identify the stress and drill the whole chunk⁵².

Songs are a useful lexical resource. Before listening, give learners the words of a song with some collocations blanked out. Ask them to work in pairs to predict how many words have been blanked out from each space. They then listen for the exact words. If there are any patterns in the song (for example, a number of second conditional sentences), learners can be asked to identify these sentences, and write more sentences using the same structure which fit the theme of the song.

Reading

Prepare a table which includes half or part of some of the multi-word items in a text. Learners then scan the text to complete the table with the other half of the collocations.

Short texts can be used to prepare for and practise reading aloud. Pauses normally come at the end of a chunk, while content words are stressed. If learners mark pauses and stressed words, this will improve their reading aloud, as well as helping them to 'notice' chunks.

Reading activities can also be used for consciousness-raising. After answering comprehension questions, learners are asked to put the original text away, and are given a new version with some of the key collocations blanked out. Working in pairs, they have to reconstruct the collocations, before checking with the original.

Recycling collocations

Learners are unlikely to remember chunks after seeing them just once, so it will be necessary to recycle them in subsequent classes. Most traditional vocabulary-recycling activities can be adapted for use with multi-word items, but here are a few ideas:⁵³

Give learners discussion questions including the chunks. Personalisation can make the language more memorable.

Pelmanism, i.e. the memory game where learners have to find matching halves of collocations from cards placed face-down on the table. They turn over two cards, and

⁵¹ Lewis, Michael *The Lexical Approach* (LTP 1993)

⁵² Sökmen, Anita J 'Current trends in teaching second language vocabulary' in Schmitt and McCarthy

⁵³ Coe, Norman 'Vocabulary must be learnt, not taught' MET Vol 6 No3 July 1997

keep them if they go together. Prepare a list of collocations recently seen in class. Divide the class into teams of 3-4 students, and give each team a piece of paper. Write a collocation from the list on the board. The first team to write a correct sentence including that collocation gets a point. Continue until you've exhausted the list, or until one team reaches a specified number of points.

A few minutes before the end of a class, ask learners working individually to write down all the new collocations / chunks they've seen in that class. They can then compare together, or if there's enough time, give definitions for their partner to guess the chunks. This could also be done at the beginning of a class to recycle language from the previous class.

Word Games and Puzzles: Engage students in word games, such as crossword puzzles, word searches, or word association activities. These activities prompt students to explore and discover lexical relationships, connections, and meanings in an interactive and enjoyable way. Games in lexicography can be diverse because of many different topics that can be covered from language learning, spelling, alphabet, grammar, history and culture, etc. There are also many different types of educational games such as quizzes, crossword puzzles, jigsaw puzzles, and unique games that have their rules and playing mechanics. Some online tools on lexicographic sites such as Scrabble Word Finder, while not being considered as a game, can help players when they are playing board game Scrabble where the goal is to match letter tiles to get words that exist in the dictionary.. Some sites like Macmillan Dictionary, in addition to games, have written assignments and tasks which are stored as PDF documents⁵⁴. Some of these documents may even ask a player to use a dictionary while solving assignments.

However, gamification elements cannot be present interactively on their own on paper since there is no visual feedback or sometimes there is nobody scoring and making sure that the player follows the rules of the game. This is not a problem when using computer games or applications since they automatically score your activities based on their algorithm and can restrict user interaction with educational content based on their design.

Corpus Linguistics: Introduce students to corpus linguistics tools, such as online corpora or concordance software, which allow them to explore real-life language usage patterns and examine word frequencies, collocations, and semantic associations. Students can identify patterns and generalize lexical rules based on their observations.

Vocabulary Journals: Encourage students to maintain vocabulary journals where they record new words encountered during their daily reading or listening activities. They can categorize words based on word formation, meaning, or word families. This

⁵⁴ Macmillan Dictionary. Language puzzles. 02.05.2013. <https://www.macmillandictionary.com/language-games/puzzles> (14.6.2019)

activity fosters independent exploration and reflection on lexical items. Vocabulary journals are tools that students can use to actively engage with new words and expand their vocabulary. They serve as personal records where students can collect and organize new words, their meanings, and examples of usage. Here are some key points about vocabulary journals:

Word Collection: Vocabulary journals allow students to record and collect new words they encounter in their reading, listening, or other language activities. This includes unfamiliar words, idioms, collocations, and expressions.

Word Meaning and Usage: Students can write down the meanings of the words they collect and provide example sentences or contexts in which the words are used. This helps deepen their understanding of word meanings and how they are applied in different contexts.

Categorization and Organization: Vocabulary journals enable students to categorize words based on themes, word families, or parts of speech. This organization helps students see connections and patterns among words and supports their retention and retrieval of vocabulary.

Personalization and Ownership: Vocabulary journals are personal to each student, allowing them to take ownership of their learning. Students can personalize their journals by adding notes, comments, or personal examples related to the words they have collected.

Reflective Learning: Vocabulary journals provide an opportunity for students to reflect on their learning progress and monitor their vocabulary development over time. They can review and revisit their journals, reinforcing their understanding and revisiting words for reinforcement.

Independent Learning: Vocabulary journals promote independent learning as students actively seek out new words and take responsibility for expanding their vocabulary. They encourage students to be curious and engaged learners, continuously seeking out new words and recording them in their journals.

Vocabulary Expansion: Regular use of vocabulary journals helps students build a robust and varied vocabulary repertoire. By actively recording, organizing, and reviewing words, students strengthen their vocabulary skills and improve their overall language proficiency.

Vocabulary Practice: Vocabulary journals can also serve as a source of vocabulary practice. Students can create flashcards, quizzes, or games based on the words in their journals to reinforce their learning and test their knowledge.

Overall, vocabulary journals provide a valuable tool for students to actively engage with and expand their vocabulary. They promote independent learning, organization, and reflective practice, helping students develop a strong vocabulary base and enhance their overall language skills.

Deductive Materials

Lexical Resource Books: Use dictionaries, thesauri, and other lexical resource books to provide explicit explanations, definitions, synonyms, and antonyms of words. Teachers can guide students through these resources to familiarize them with different lexical categories, word meanings, and usage.

Word Analysis Worksheets: Provide worksheets that require students to analyze and categorize words based on their morphological properties, such as affixes, roots, or word families. These worksheets can focus on word formation processes, such as affixation, compounding, or derivation.

Vocabulary Exercises: Design exercises that focus on specific lexical phenomena, such as synonym/antonym identification, collocation matching, or sentence completion using target vocabulary. These exercises help students practice applying lexical knowledge in context and reinforce their understanding of lexical relationships.

Classroom Discussions: Engage students in structured discussions about lexical topics, such as word formation, semantic change, or lexical borrowing. Teachers can provide explanations, examples, and guided questions to promote deductive reasoning and comprehension of lexical concepts.

Classroom discussions are interactive and collaborative conversations that take place among students and teachers within the classroom setting. These discussions provide a platform for students to actively participate, share ideas, exchange perspectives, and engage in meaningful dialogue.

Active Learning: Classroom discussions promote active learning by encouraging students to think critically, analyze information, and contribute their own insights. Through discussions, students can construct their understanding of the subject matter and develop higher-order thinking skills.

Student Engagement: Discussions foster student engagement as they create an inclusive and participatory learning environment. Students are given opportunities to express their thoughts, ask questions, and engage in intellectual debates, which helps them feel valued and connected to the learning process.

Collaboration and Social Skills: Classroom discussions cultivate collaboration and social skills among students. By listening to others, responding thoughtfully, and building on each other's ideas, students develop effective communication skills, empathy, and respectful interaction.

Multiple Perspectives: Discussions provide a platform for students to encounter diverse viewpoints and experiences. This exposure to different perspectives broadens students' understanding, promotes empathy, and encourages critical thinking by challenging their own assumptions and biases.

Language Development: Classroom discussions contribute to language development as students engage in oral communication, practice expressing their ideas,

and refine their language skills. They learn to articulate their thoughts clearly, use appropriate vocabulary, and construct coherent arguments.

Scaffolding Knowledge: Discussions can be used to scaffold knowledge and deepen understanding. Teachers can guide discussions by asking probing questions, providing clarifications, and connecting students' contributions to the topic at hand. This scaffolding supports students' cognitive development and helps them make meaningful connections.

Active Listening: Classroom discussions foster active listening skills as students learn to attentively listen to their peers, consider different perspectives, and respond thoughtfully. Active listening enhances comprehension and promotes respectful and empathetic communication.

Critical Thinking: Classroom discussions stimulate critical thinking by encouraging students to analyze, evaluate, and synthesize information. They learn to support their ideas with evidence, consider counterarguments, and develop reasoning skills.

To ensure effective classroom discussions, it is important for teachers to create a safe and inclusive environment, establish clear guidelines for participation, and provide scaffolding and guidance when necessary. By incorporating meaningful discussions into the classroom, educators can foster student engagement, deepen understanding, and promote the development of essential skills for lifelong learning.

It's important to note that the choice of materials and approach should consider the students' language proficiency level, learning objectives, and the complexity of the lexical concepts being taught. A combination of inductive and deductive materials will provide a comprehensive and engaging learning experience, enabling students to develop a deeper understanding of lexicology and its application in language use.

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